

Navigating Digital Preservation in Modern Libraries: Opportunities and Obstacles

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Abstract

Digital preservation in modern libraries presents a dynamic landscape of opportunities and obstacles.

Purpose of the Study: *This study explores the multifaceted aspects of digital preservation, highlighting the potential for enhanced accessibility, collaboration, and technological advancements. It also addresses the significant challenges posed by technological obsolescence, financial constraints, skill gaps, and legal and ethical issues.*

Methodology: *Through a comprehensive analysis of current practices and emerging trends, the study provides insights into effective strategies for navigating the complexities of digital preservation.*

Findings/Conclusion: *The findings underscore the importance of continuous investment in technology, training, and policy development to ensure the long-term preservation and accessibility of digital collections. By addressing these challenges, libraries can leverage digital preservation to enhance their role as custodians of knowledge in the digital age.*

Study Type: *Review paper*

Keywords: Navigating digital preservation, modern libraries, practices

Introduction

Over the years, libraries have been utilising information resources both in print and electronic formats to meet the diverse information needs of their users. Navigating digital preservation in modern libraries presents both exciting opportunities and significant obstacles. As libraries increasingly digitise their collections to enhance accessibility and reach, they face challenges in ensuring the long-term preservation of digital materials (Masenya & Ngulube, 2021). Information service delivery in libraries is hinged on the availability of adequate information resources. Information resources are, therefore, considered a vital component of every library, regardless of type and size. However, with the advancement in Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) and their adoption in libraries, there is a drastic shift from print to electronic/digital information resources. In order to maximise the potential of digital resources, libraries are retrospectively converting their print resources to digital formats. Thus, these resources could be either created digitally or by conversion from print to digital forms. Information resources in digital forms are those resources that are accessible through digital devices such as computers, tablets and smartphones. Digital information resources provide access to a wide range of information and, as such, constitute a rich source of information for educational and non-educational purposes for different categories of information users. Examples of these resources include E-books, E-serials, E-reports, E-theses, E-pictures/photographs, databases, online encyclopedias,

Listserve and digital libraries. With the growing volume of data, participants emphasised sufficient planning and preservation actions to sustain future access and improve the discovery of archived digital content (Wong & Chiu, 2024).

Digital resources, similar to print resources, have a lifespan, which implies that they require preservation to elongate their lifespan. Although they are more durable and lasting compared to prints, they are also prone to certain deteriorative agents, which calls for their preservation. According to Cornell University Library in Lakshminarasimhappa (2014), the preservation of digital resources includes a wide variety of operations intended to increase the functional life of machine-readable files and safeguard them against media failure, physical loss, and obsolescence. With the high adoption and utilisation of these resources in libraries of the 21st century, scholarly attention has now been given to their preservation practices. Digital preservation is a fundamental responsibility of every library that intends to continuously deliver effective and efficient information services to its users for a prolonged time. Thus, the practice of digital preservation is crucial to librarianship and, by extension, Library and Information Science (LIS) as a field of knowledge. Consequently, knowledge of digital preservation practices, which this chapter presents, makes a relevant component in LIS literature.

The paper attempts to provide an understanding of the concept of digital preservation by first giving insight into the general concept of preservation of library materials and then restricting it to digital preservation. The paper also attempts to provide an answer to the question of why digital preservation. This question will be answered by asserting reasons for digital preservation among libraries in the current dispensation. In addition, the challenges faced by digital preservation practices in libraries and their prospects were examined. Thereafter, some of the ways forward will be proposed.

Understanding digital preservation

Preservation in the parlance of librarianship is as old as the library itself. The establishment of early libraries was proposed because of the necessity for the preservation of human records and those of human civilisations. Thus, one of the fundamental and age-long roles of the library was to preserve information-carrying materials. In this context, preservation is considered as every practice or action that slows down the deterioration of information materials, with the intention of elongating their useful lifespan. According to Badawi (2012), preservation is the act of safeguarding and protecting library materials from possible harm or destruction. It includes all activities and practices required to keep library materials in the best possible condition for a long time for better information service delivery. Early practices of preservation in libraries dated back to the 19th century were libraries made use of acid-free papers, deacidification of acid-based papers, monitoring human activities within the library, storing their materials in a temperature and humidity-controlled environment, and digitisation, which produces a digital format of library information resources.

While some library resources are converted or reformatted into digital format to preserve them (digitisation), others are created/born digital, inspired by the current technological revolution. This has increased the amount of digital resources in today's libraries and precipitated the need for digital preservation. Day (2006), cited in Masenya and Ngulube (2021), describes digital preservation as the application of preservative measures, methods, techniques and strategies to ensure access to both reformatted and born-digital content. In order to ensure sustainable digital preservation practices, three vital elements need to be addressed, which Corrado and Moulaison (2014) referred to as the digital preservation triad. They consider the aspects or activities that comprise sustainable digital preservation; they are content-centred, management-related and technological-related activities. Content is primary

to every preservation practice, as every other activity revolves around it. Digital content is the essence of every digital preservation practice, and managing this content involves collection, organisation, categorisation, and structuring. Management-related activities include human resources, strategies, and policies that drive sustainable digital preservation practices. Meanwhile, the technology-related activities involve implementing digital preservation systems like metadata systems and digital repositories. These three aspects of digital preservation, known as the digital preservation triad, must be in sync and work systematically for success in digital preservation practices.

Figure 1 Digital Preservation Triad by Corrado and Moulaison (2014)

Corrado and Moulaison (2014) highlighted the three elements of a sustainable digital preservation program: management-related activities, technologically related activities, and content-focused activities. Corrado and Moulaison (2014) identified three critical elements for a sustainable digital preservation program: management-related activities, technologically related activities, and content-focused activities. Management-related activities involve strategic planning, policy development, and administrative oversight necessary to ensure the long-term success of digital preservation efforts. This includes securing funding, establishing clear guidelines and standards, and fostering a culture of preservation within the organisation. Effective management ensures that digital preservation is prioritised and integrated into the overall mission of the library or institution. Technologically related activities encompass the technical infrastructure and tools required for digital preservation. This includes selecting appropriate hardware and software, implementing robust storage solutions, and ensuring the interoperability of digital formats. Technological activities also involve regular maintenance, updates, and migration of digital content to prevent obsolescence and ensure continued accessibility. Content-focused activities are centered on the actual digital materials being preserved. This includes the selection, appraisal, and digitisation of content, as well as the creation of metadata and documentation to support discovery and access. Content-focused activities also involve ongoing monitoring and quality control to ensure the integrity and authenticity of digital materials.

Together, these three elements form a comprehensive framework for sustainable digital preservation. By addressing management, technology, and content, libraries and institutions can create resilient preservation programs that safeguard digital materials for future generations.

In essence, the image below shows what digital preservation is set to achieve. Digital preservation aims to achieve several key objectives, including ensuring long-term access to digital materials despite technological changes, protecting cultural heritage, and enhancing accessibility to a global audience. It

supports research and education by providing reliable access to digital resources and ensures compliance with legal and ethical standards, such as copyright and data privacy regulations. Additionally, digital preservation plays a crucial role in disaster recovery by safeguarding digital materials from loss due to natural calamities, hardware failures, or cyber-attacks. By achieving these objectives, digital preservation maintains the integrity, authenticity, and accessibility of digital content, ensuring that valuable information is preserved and available for future use.

Figure 2 Digital Preservation Goals (American Library Association, n.d)

Why digital preservation?

The practice of digital preservation is considered a disruptive innovation, especially among libraries that hitherto have been carrying out the preservation of print resources. Some of the reasons why libraries engage in the preservation of their digital resources include:

- i. **Proliferation of digital resources:** The current dispensation has experienced a fast proliferation of information resources, while libraries are trying to keep up with preserving these contents for the future (David & Soyemi, 2021). Raju in Masenya and Ngulube (2021) noted that this proliferation has altered the traditional academic library. This has promoted the urgent need to rethink the way information resources are preserved to avoid extinction. Thus, the preservation of digital resources has become imperative due to the realities of the digital revolution and the aftermath of the proliferation of digital resources (Gautam, 2021).
- ii. **The visibility reason:** Authors are faced with the problem of not being able to access their research and gain visibility, and this problem can be resolved by sustainable digital preservation practice (Masenya & Ngulube, 2020). Uploading electronic resources into digital repository systems like Institutional Repositories (IR) gives these resources a high level of discoverability, which makes the resources visible for use and advantageous for both information users and authors of the information resources. Thus, digital preservation will contribute to solving the problem of research visibility, which Ezema in Anyaoku et al. (2019) noted to be a problem in scholarly publications in Africa. A typical example of

this is reported by Kulhavy et al. (2017) when they said that ScholarWorks, which is an institutional repository of Stephen F. Austin State University (SFASU), provides permanent links (URL) to digital resources uploaded on the repository, which increases their discoverability and visibility globally.

- iii. **Collaboration and Resource Sharing:** Digital preservation fosters collaboration among libraries, enabling them to share resources, expertise, and best practices. This can lead to the development of comprehensive digital repositories and collaborative preservation initiatives.
- iv. **Economic reasons:** With most libraries' budgetary constraints and the exponential production of information materials, libraries cannot allow their digital resources to be damaged and destroyed prematurely. Most digital resources are expensive to procure, and preserving them to extend their lifespan makes economic sense. Also, the fact that several people can access and use the same digital resources at the same time is a financial advantage over print resources. This justifies digitisation and digital preservation.
- v. **Long-term access:** Digital preservation allows libraries to make their collections accessible to a global audience, breaking geographical barriers. It ensures that the information in digital resources remains accessible to users over a long period. Thus, a fundamental goal of digital preservation is to ensure continued access to digital materials for as long as necessary by avoiding deterioration. Information resources in digital form, when preserved, guarantee long-term access. Velmurugan (2013) affirmed that access is one of the fundamental principles of digital preservation, which should be considered a matter of policy for every library.
- vi. **Sustainable information service delivery:** digital information resources are critical tools for providing information services. The ability to have digital material available for such purpose for a long time will be highly dependent on digital preservation practices. As such, to sustain the delivery of information services, libraries must strive to ensure their digital materials are in good condition for access at all times.

Challenges of digital preservation in libraries

1. **Lack of funds:** Digital preservation requires significant financial investments in technology, infrastructure, and training. Nigerian libraries have continued to lament the poor funding available to them. This has become a hindrance to the deployment of innovative technologies and practices like digital preservation practice. Digital preservation runs on systems and infrastructures that require funding to set up. In the absence of such financing, it becomes difficult to effectively practice digital preservation. According to Chattopadhyay (2006), funds to handle technological and organisational advancement are an obstacle to long-term digital preservation. The study by Jimada (2015) also showed that inadequate fund remains a key challenge to the implementation of digital preservation in Nigerian university libraries.
2. **Digital preservation policy:** Most libraries, especially in Nigeria, lack a digital preservation policy. The policy is an essential part of digital preservation practices as it dictates the methodology, what materials should be preserved, and the rules for preservation. It also addresses concerns associated with digital preservation, like copyright.

3. **Managerial support:** The introduction of innovations or practices in libraries will succeed in measuring management's support. First, the vision of digital preservation practice needs to be embraced by management, then communicated downwards and monitored for success to be assured. However, the practice of digital preservation is struggling in Nigeria because of a lack of managerial support. Most of the library management has not accepted the prospects of digital preservation as critical to 21st-century library service delivery. As such, they fail to provide the needed support in terms of motivation and technical and infrastructural facilities. Thus, lack of management support invariably poses organisational challenges for digital preservation practice
4. **Lack of standards:** Libraries do not seem to have a uniform standard for preserving digital resources. Hedstrom, in Igberaese et al. (2014), noted that the absence of established standards for digital preservation is a challenge to libraries. Standards ensure that these resources are accessible over time and that the processes of preserving them, as well as their description (metadata), are uniform and consistent.
5. **Lack of technical skills:** The preservation of digital resources requires a high level of technical skill, which is currently missing among library personnel. There is a dearth of preservation experts in libraries, which could hinder effective digital preservation practices. According to Masenya (2018), libraries are challenged with the management of hybrid resources, which require technical skills. If these skill sets are missing among the personnel, it breeds poor management of these resources. Libraries may face challenges in recruiting and retaining staff with the expertise needed to manage digital preservation efforts.
6. **Legal Issues:** Digital preservation raises questions that are legally and ethically complex. Ownership of digital resources is a vital issue of consideration in digital archiving. Intellectual ownership could be a challenge for libraries when archiving electronic information resources, especially for E-journals where publishers could reserve certain rights. This corroborates Chattopadhyay's assertion (2006) that intellectual property rights could impede the preservation of digital objects through systematic copying. Velmurugan (2013) noted that Copyright and intellectual property rights (IPR) are some of the challenges experienced in digital preservation. The author further stated that in storing digital materials for conservation, new copies of the materials are created with the same status as the digital original, which could portend copyright issues. Libraries must consciously navigate these issues to ensure compliance and protect the rights of users and creators.

Prospects of digital preservation in libraries

Regardless of the possible challenges that could be associated with digital preservation, it is still an endeavour to be highly considered by libraries given its enormous prospects, some of which are:

1. **Remote and multiple accesses:** One distinct feature of digital resources is their nature of access. When digital resources are preserved in an information system, they can be accessed remotely, which enhances remote learning. People can access the contents of a library from the comfort of their homes through the practice of digital preservation. Also, multiple accesses to a particular content are made possible, which caters to the deficiency posed by limited copies of information resources. Lakshminarasimhappa and Veena (2014) asserted that with the digitisation of materials, global and multiple accesses are made possible, which increases the usability of information resources.

2. **Longevity of digital records**—Digital preservation ensures that digital documents can be retrieved, rendered, and interpreted by future users, regardless of the effects of changes in technology, format, or standards. This is because data backup, migration, emulation, proper metadata creation and quality assurance are techniques that ensure continued access. This protects the authenticity, integrity, and reliability of digital records and prevents their loss or degradation.
3. **Reuse and repurposing of digital data**—Data loss, degradation, and obsolescence are critical issues that beset digital data. However, with proper digital preservation standards and formats, more people can use digital data for much longer, regardless of time and place.
4. **Protect the cultural and historical heritage of humanity** – capturing, proper curation, and preservation of documented historical events reflecting the diversity and richness of our collective human experiences has become easier to attain. Sharing and disseminating this information across time and space, thereby fostering knowledge creation and innovation.

The Way Forward

Digital preservation projects require enormous physical and human resources and can be challenging if they are not properly planned and executed.

1. **Management Support for digital preservation** – digital preservation is a commitment that requires support of all, from libraries and the relevant stakeholders. However, the management plays a very important role in the success or otherwise of any digital preservation activity. Allocating the needed resources – human, financial, and technical required for the process, setting clear roles and responsibilities for the staff involved in the process, developing and implementing policies and procedures and defining the action plan. Management must also monitor and evaluate the performance and outcomes of the process and promote awareness and advocacy for digital preservation both within and outside the organisation.
2. **Set and stick to Standards**– standards are very important in digital preservation; they help set clear yardsticks for defining necessities, gauging outcomes, and supporting existing and future systems. Moving forward, Nigerian libraries must source and adapt set digital preservation standards like the Open Archival Information Systems (OAIS) model, with a blend of policies related to digital excellence in digital preservation. Also, interacting with countries, agencies, and organisations with functioning policies and learning the challenges and strategies they adopted to surmount the issues encountered while implementing or domiciling the adopted standards.
3. **Improve Technical Expertise**– capacity building is a pertinent component for success and excellence in the drive towards digital preservation excellence. Training, workshops, and exposure of personnel to international best practices in the field will go a long way in improving the state of the art in digital preservation in Nigeria. Six key aspects require adequate technical expertise for success in digital preservation activities. Managing data, understanding and handling file formats, proper curation and metadata management, records storage, preservation actions, and lastly, accessing the preserved digital content for a very long period.
4. **Proper Management of associated Legal Issues** – getting around the legal challenges of compliance with copyright, intellectual property, licensing, privacy and confidentiality, and other related issues requires a clear awareness of these issues first while having clarity on

complying with relevant laws and regulations, making sure communication with stakeholders of digital materials like creators, owners, regulators, and so on. This is to ensure permissions and needed licenses are sought for preservation activities. This is to ensure legal compliance and accountability on the part of professionals handling digital preservation activities.

Conclusion

As technologies continue to advance, born-digital and retrospectively converted information will continue to proliferate. This geometric growth will require carefully planned digital preservation strategies to keep up with the information emanating from the continued intellectual flow. Libraries have an immense role to play, albeit authors, institutions and statutory agencies in Nigeria to ensure long-term access to the intellectual output from its ivory towers. This is because of the ephemeral nature of digital information. Making adequate plans for storing, accessing, transferring, and archiving digital information will go a long way in determining the success of any digital preservation strategy that is designed and adopted by libraries in Nigeria. With a lack of digital preservation policies at most libraries, a national digitisation strategy, national reference service strategy, national storage strategy, national preservation strategy, transfer policy, or digital transition policy has been a major challenge in Nigeria at the moment. Managing digital records remains a question that library administrators and professionals must solve. Digital preservation is clearly not a technical challenge alone; it has social and organisational dimensions. This is because it requires a shared vision, common understanding, and coordination among different actors and sectors to continually adapt to the changing expectations of society coupled with the dynamic nature of digital preservation and the benefit it provides humanity.

Conflict of Interest

The authors affirm that the research, which was a paper previously presented at a conference, has been improved upon and was conducted without any commercial or financial ties that could be seen as potential conflicts of interest. Each author made unique contributions to the research, from its initial conceptualisation to its completion.

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